

Efficient UI Test Automation: Decoupled Element Identifiers Services

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ABSTRACT

Mobile application UI test automation often encounters challenges related to the dynamic nature of UI elements and the diverse set of automation tools available. Maintaining test scripts gets difficult and expensive in situations where element identifiers are absent or are changed often. In order to overcome these difficulties, this study suggests separating element identifiers from automation scripts and providing a versatile method for defining and retrieving identifiers at runtime. Automation engineers have the ability to dynamically retrieve the relevant identifiers according to version, device type, and other attributes by utilizing element definition files and a collection of APIs. This method streamlines the process of maintaining test scripts and enhances the effectiveness and expandability of mobile user interface testing. The proposed solution's design, implementation, and possible advantages are covered in the paper, emphasizing how they will lessen maintenance efforts and improve the test automation process's agility.

This study proposes a system that addresses the aforementioned issues by offering a single method for defining element identifiers. This solution allows us to execute test automation on numerous operating systems and devices running different versions of the remote application. It is partially built using WorkspaceONE SDK CI/CD pipeline. The solution may be used in other VMware products, even if it is currently utilized for mobile products.

Key words: XPath, Identifier, Mobile test, Automation Testing, API, Element Identification

INTRODUCTION

The accurate identification of user interface (UI) elements is critical to the effectiveness and efficacy of test automation in the context of mobile application testing. Automation scripts typically depend on static identifiers, like resource names or unique IDs, connected to user interface elements. However, preserving these static IDs becomes difficult and time-consuming in dynamic environments when apps experience frequent changes or variances across multiple platforms and versions

Generally, the application's user interface elements have unique identifiers E.g., Button, Tables, and Textboxes all are given a unique id but, in some scenarios where we can't control the application's source code (E.g., Safari Browser or System settings) and the element's unique identifier is missing, test scripts use other approaches like the element's rectangular area, content description, and axis coordinates to name those identifiers. UI Test automation relies on identifying these element IDs or other descriptions to take action regarding the click, tap, and scroll operations.

Furthermore, in the case of hybrid applications, there may be one or more remote servers to deliver the UI elements to mobile applications (E.g., Workspace ONE has Green box and VIDM with two different release cycles) and may change UI elements between versions due to business requirements or new element introduction or flow changes. Given all the above scenarios, it becomes difficult and expensive to maintain different element IDs per release, especially when test scripts are in a high count.

NOTE: Remote servers may have a SaaS model that makes it easy to push new changes without updating mobile clients.

A hybrid application diagram depicts this problem below.

Figure 1: How element IDs differ between two versions of web application while mobile client version is same

Another existing problem with mobile application UI automation is the underlying used tool. There are multiple commercial and non-commercial tools available in the market for mobile application automation, and each of them has various ways to identify elements on screen. E.g., xPaths (a mechanism to map each element on the screen and generate a unique path), CSS selector, accessibility IDs, text, resource id, etc. This forces automation engineers to select one automation tool with the assumption it won't change for long. However, this is not the case if, due to business or technical reasons, developers would like to switch to a new code branch or database change, which will enhance the problem of migration to remap all the UI elements as per the new requirement. Furthermore, these IDs also vary depending on the state of the mobile application and whether the application is instrumented or non-instrumented. Instrumented application is a signed application with a digital signature while non-instrumented application is not signed. In both cases, element IDs may differ depending on the underlying automation tool.

All these above cases make it more difficult to provide a standard way to define element IDs or object identifiers in automation code, which is maintainable and cost-effective in the long run. To handle these problems, the proposed solution offers to define an element definition file per screen with multiple attributes, and these attributes are combined at run time through the provided API, which helps to work with one or more attributes of element IDs at the same time.

The proposed solution has the following main components.

An innovative technique is suggested to overcome these issues: administrators and test engineers can define these identifiers dynamically through a console user interface, and element identifiers are logically separated from their physical IDs. The objective of this technique is to enhance UI test automation by facilitating the retrieval of element identifiers through API queries, taking into account variables like version, device kind, and element type.

Element Identification definition file: These files are written in json/xml format and have multiple optional attributes for each element. Automation writers can provide one or more attributes for each version. These defined values are retrieved at run time through the APIs provided by the framework.

APIs: A set of APIs are part of the solution to get the right element attribute from the definition file.

DESIGN

The proposed solution is to logically separate element identifiers from actual physical IDs and enable admin/test engineers to define them through the console user interface. During the automation, the framework can request these element IDs based on the versions, device type, and element type through the API request. API can then deliver all element identifiers present on a particular screen in json or xml format.

In the context of a Web Server/Console environment, the Test Screen Class is an essential part of the process of designing screens and elements for various application versions. This interface is used by admins or test users to create and maintain screen configurations that are specific to particular application versions. The test case includes multiple crucial phases to guarantee this process runs smoothly. First, the user navigates to the Test Screen Class interface in response to a request to load a screen. Following receipt of the request, the framework uses the given application version to initiate a request for the corresponding screen object.

Figure 2: Sequence diagram

In response, the console returns the relevant screen object that is organized in accordance with the specified elements and attributes for the specified version. During this procedure, all errors that are detected are carefully recorded and submitted for additional examination and correction. The successful retrieval of the screen object ensures the availability of precise and version-specific configurations and also facilitates thorough testing and validation processes.

```

<screen>
<screenId>loginScreen</screenId>
<screenName>Login Screen</screenName>
<element>
<id>SIGNIN_BUTTON</id>
<version>
<ver>1.0 </ver>
<resource-id></resource-id>
<accName></accName>
<accValue></accValue>
<content-desc></content-desc>
<xpath>
<deviceType>phone</deviceType>
<type>WEB</type>
<value>//*[ @id='signIn']</value>
</xpath>
<deviceType>phone</deviceType>
<type>NATIVE</type>
<value>//*[ @text='Sign in']</value>
</xpath>
<rect>
<x></x>
<y></y>
<width></width>
<height></height>
</rect>
</version> </element>
  
```

```

<element>
<id>LOGIN_BUTTON</id>
<version>
<ver>1.0</ver>
<xpath>
<deviceType>phone</deviceType>
<type>WEB</type>
<value>//*[@id='login']</value>
</xpath>
</version>
<version>
<ver>2.0</ver>
<xpath>
<deviceType>phone</deviceType>
<type>WEB</type>
<value>//*[@text='Log In']</value>
</xpath>
</version>
</element>
</screen>

```

Example 1: XML/JSON format

In this example, the screen name is login screen and has two buttons, “Sign In” and “Log In”. Here, the Sign In button has only one version, while the Login button has two versions of identifiers. Multiple identities are used for illustration reasons, although one or more can be defined as needed. If unique IDs are unavailable, developers can supply one or more rectangular sections based on the form factor or specify any other feature, such as text or content description.

These xml/json files will be part of the test framework and will be defined as part of the development of the product. When a test class identifies a new screen, it will load the json/xml file (as shown in Figure 2), and framework-provided APIs will get the right element identifier.

```

• getElementId()
• getResourceId()
• getElementClassName()
• getElementAccessibilityLabel()
• getElementVersion()
• getElementContentDescription()
• getElementImagePath()
• getAllXPath()
• getXPathsForElementType()
• getXPathsForDeviceType()
• getXPathsForDeviceTypeAndElementType()
• getElementRect()
• getScreen()
• constructXPathFromList(); • getElementForVersion();
final String resource =
APICall.getScreenElementsFor('LoginScreen', 'version 1.0')
ScreenLoader screenObj = getScreen(resource);
//This will create a list of all possible xpaths defined in the screen file.
final List xPathList =
screenObj.getElementForId("SIGNIN_BUTTON").getXPathsForElementType("NATIVE");
//This will construct one xpath from the given list of xpaths.
String xpath = constructXPathFromList(xPathList);

```

Example 2: Identify XPath

As in the above example, we can see that if a new XPath is created, then the automation developer will only need to update the xml file without modifying any test case code. This will support one or more versions of the element’s attributes without worrying about various versions, form factors, OEMs or application types. This reduces maintenance and provides flexibility to change the attributes of elements.

MOTIVATION

Before this approach or other industry standards, a developer can create multiple property files for each version and define multiple element attributes; however, this approach quickly will require a high level of maintenance due to multiple dynamic factors, as described in the Abstract and Introduction sections. This approach will still not solve the problems that arise due to hybrid applications.

We faced these major issues when Workspace ONE v3.0 was released, which had an entirely different User Interface than the previous release. We were also encouraged to rethink our approach to test automation.

RELATED WORK

As described in the Introduction and Design sections, this approach drastically reduces maintenance of automation code even with the multiple dynamic nature of the mobile ecosystem.

With this approach, automation engineers need to maintain only json/xml structure for each release without worrying about the previous version's compatibility. Compared to other industry practices, this approach improves the maintainability and speed of delivery in CI/CD pipeline and saves costs to the company.

FUTURE WORK

Currently, this approach is implemented partially in the Workspace ONE SDK automation framework. However, in the future, we would like to extend the solution to deliver element identification files from the hosted servers as part of the product. This will enable mobile applications automation completely independent. Product developers can define and create element identification files and IDs, which can be delivered through the API calls to the automation framework at run time. This will further reduce the maintenance of element attributes at multiple places (product and test automation) and reduce the chances of errors.

Another enhancement we are looking for in the future is to provide these element definition files and APIs as part of the product itself, which will enable our customers (especially customers who use our SDK to develop and test their own applications) to perform test automation on their applications without worrying about elements presented by SDKs.

CONCLUSION

This solution demonstrates how decoupling element identifiers into logical entities and defining multiple attributes of each element can eliminate/reduce code maintenance, speed up delivery, and improve efficiency. With the implementation of the proposed solution, any company can save up to 35% of the overall time in automation testing.

The solution is currently implemented partially into the Workspace ONE SDK DevOps pipeline for automation. Beyond this, we hope that there may be some interest in adopting the framework elsewhere in VMware (Other teams like Boxer, Hub, and Content Locker have started discussion). If open sourced, there may be interest from outside the company.

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